

Salivary Amylase as a Biomarker of Periodontal Diseases

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Abstract:

Salivary amylase, an enzyme primarily involved in starch digestion, has gained attention as a potential biomarker for periodontal diseases due to its role in modulating bacterial growth within the oral cavity. This review examines the role of salivary amylase in periodontal diseases, focusing on its diagnostic potential and clinical relevance. The study utilized online databases, including PubMed, Scopus, and Medline, alongside manual searches to ensure comprehensive coverage. Studies investigating salivary amylase levels in individuals with periodontal diseases over the past decade were included.

Exclusion criteria encompassed non-English articles, non-peer-reviewed studies, review articles, animal studies, and research involving children (<17 years old), individuals with systemic diseases, or smokers. A total of 289 articles were identified through database and manual searches, with eight studies meeting the inclusion criteria for final analysis. Among the included studies, several reported significant differences in salivary amylase levels between individuals with gingivitis, chronic periodontitis, and healthy periodontium. Some studies failed to find significant differences in salivary amylase levels between periodontal disease groups and healthy controls. Certain studies emphasized the influence of periodontal treatment on salivary amylase levels. Salivary amylase shows promise as a biomarker for assessing periodontal health and monitoring treatment outcomes. Salivary amylase demonstrates potential as a biomarker for periodontal health and post-treatment outcomes, though inconsistencies in findings highlight the need for standardized methodologies.

Keywords: *amylase, biomarker, gingivitis, periodontitis, saliva.*

Introduction

Periodontal diseases encompass a group of conditions affecting periodontal tissues, primarily driven by infection and inflammation (Sanz, D'Aiuto, Deanfield, & Fernandez-Avilés, 2010). These diseases are widespread, impacting 20-50% of the global population (Albandar & Rams, 2002). Risk factors such as age, smoking, diabetes mellitus, poor oral hygiene, certain medications, stress, hormonal changes, and genetic predisposition significantly increase susceptibility to periodontal diseases (M. Nazir

et al., 2020; M. A. Nazir, 2017). These conditions can negatively impact overall quality of life, underscoring the importance of early diagnosis and timely periodontal treatment to improve patient outcomes (Wong, Yap, & Allen, 2021).

Recently, there has been growing interest in identifying non-invasive and cost-effective biomarkers for periodontal diseases. Salivary amylase, an enzyme involved in starch digestion, has emerged as a potential biomarker. Beyond its digestive role, alpha-amylase contributes to the formation of the acquired pellicle on tooth

surfaces (Fábián, Hermann, Beck, Fejérdy, & Fábián, 2012) and exhibits antimicrobial properties, including inhibiting the growth of *Porphyromonas gingivalis* and biofilm formation by *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans* through interactions with bacterial lipopolysaccharides (Baik et al., 2013; Ochiai et al., 2014). Elevated levels of salivary amylase have been observed in individuals with periodontal diseases (Kejriwal, Bhandary, Thomas, & Kumari, 2014; Mani et al., 2023; Neha, Maya, & Rakhewar Purushottam, 2018), suggesting a possible role for this enzyme in the diagnosis and assessment of these conditions.

This review explores the role of salivary amylase as a biomarker for periodontal diseases, focusing on its diagnostic value and relationship with disease severity. Furthermore, the study aims to identify gaps in the existing literature and propose directions for future research in this promising area.

Materials and Methods

The selection of studies from the utilized databases adhered to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. This review utilized several online databases, including PubMed, Scopus, and Medline. A manual search was conducted to identify additional relevant studies that might not have been retrieved through database searches. The search strategy incorporated keywords such as "salivary amylase," "salivary alpha-amylase," "periodontitis," "periodontal disease," "periodontal inflammation," "gingival inflammation," "gingivitis," "gingival recession," and "periodontal abscess."

Studies published between January 2014 and December 2024 that investigated salivary amylase in individuals with periodontal diseases were included. Exclusion criteria including non-English articles, non-peer-reviewed articles, review articles, and animal studies. To ensure a more homogeneous population, articles focusing on children (<17 years old), individuals

with systemic diseases or smoking habits were excluded. The extracted data included the author(s) and year of publication, title, population, study design, and key findings.

Results

Figure 1. PRISMA Flow Diagram of Study Selection Process

A total of 286 articles were initially identified through database searches, with an additional 3 articles found through manual searching, resulting in 289 articles for screening (Figure 1). Following the exclusion of records outside the specified timeframe of 2014-2024, 149 articles remained. After removing 58 duplicates, 91 unique articles were screened based on their titles and abstracts. Of these, 68 articles were selected for full-text assessment. Eight articles were included in the final analysis.

Table 1. Extracted Data from Included Articles

Authors	Title	Study Population	Study Design	Key Findings
Kejriwal et al., 2014	Estimation of levels of salivary mucin, amylase and total protein in gingivitis and chronic periodontitis patients	Participants: 90 individuals (aged 25–60 years). Groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 30 individuals with gingivitis • 30 individuals with chronic periodontitis • 30 individuals with healthy periodontium 	Case-control	Significant difference of salivary amylase between groups with gingivitis, chronic periodontitis, and healthy periodontium ($p < 0.001$).
Acquier, Pita, Busch, & Sánchez, 2015	Comparison of salivary levels of mucin and amylase and their relation with clinical parameters obtained from patients with aggressive and chronic periodontal disease	Participants: 80 individuals. Groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 individuals with aggressive periodontitis and 20 matched controls (aged 17–23 years) • 20 individuals with chronic periodontitis and 20 matched controls (aged 32–40 years) 	Case-control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No significant differences of salivary amylase between groups ($p > 0.05$). • A positive correlation between salivary amylase with clinical attachment loss ($p < 0.0001$) and pocket depth ($p < 0.0001$) in individuals with aggressive and chronic periodontitis.
Carolina, Rusyanti, & Susanto, 2017	Comparison of salivary alpha-amylase levels in gingivitis and periodontitis	Participants: 44 individuals (aged 30–60 years). Groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 22 individuals with gingivitis • 22 individuals with chronic periodontitis 	Cross-sectional	A significant difference of salivary amylase between groups with gingivitis and chronic periodontitis.
Neha et al., 2018	Salivary amylase as a biomarker in health and periodontal diseases	Participants: 45 individuals (aged 25–60 years). Groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 15 individuals with generalized chronic gingivitis • 15 individuals with generalized chronic periodontitis • 15 individuals with healthy periodontium 	Case-control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant difference of salivary amylase between groups with generalized chronic gingivitis, generalized chronic periodontitis, and healthy periodontium at baseline/before scaling and root planing ($p < 0.001$). • Significant differences of salivary amylase between baseline and 6 weeks after scaling and root planing in gingivitis and periodontitis group.
Develioglu, Korkmaz, Dunder, & Schlagenhauf, 2020	Investigation of the levels of different salivary stress markers in chronic periodontitis patients	Participants: 80 individuals (aged ≥ 35 years). Groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 26 individuals with mild chronic periodontitis • 39 individuals with moderate chronic periodontitis • 15 individuals with severe chronic periodontitis 	Cross-sectional	No significant differences of salivary amylase between groups ($p > 0.05$).
Mani et al., 2023	Salivary amylase and mucin in chronic periodontitis: pre/post therapy	Participants: 40 individuals (aged 25–60 years). Groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 individuals with chronic periodontitis 	Case-control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A significant difference of salivary amylase between groups with chronic periodontitis and healthy periodontium ($p < 0.001$). • A significant difference of salivary amylase between baseline

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 individuals with healthy periodontium 		and 45 days after scaling and root planing in periodontitis group.
Parlak, Buber, Gur, Karabulut, & Akalin, 2023	Statherin and alpha-amylase levels in saliva from patients with gingivitis and periodontitis	Participants: 67 individuals (aged 19–67 years). Groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 26 individuals with gingivitis • 20 individuals with periodontitis • 21 individuals with healthy periodontium 	Case-control	No significant differences of salivary amylase between groups (p=0.295).
Hashim et al., 2024	Exploring salivary alpha-amylase as a biomarker in periodontitis: a comparative analysis of disease stages and clinical correlations	Participants: 45 individuals (mean age: 38.8 ± 8.8 years). Groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10 individuals with mild periodontitis • 9 individuals with moderate periodontitis • 13 individuals with severe periodontitis • 13 individuals with healthy periodontium 	Case-control	Significant differences of salivary amylase between four groups (p=0.001). A post hoc test found significant differences in salivary amylase between individuals with mild and moderate periodontitis (p=0.0187), between individuals with moderate and severe periodontitis (p=0.00197), as well as between individuals with mild and severe periodontitis (p=0.00041).

Table 1 presents the extracted data from the included studies, all of which are observational, with no experimental studies identified. Several studies reported significant differences in salivary amylase levels among individuals with gingivitis, chronic periodontitis, and healthy periodontium. However, some studies did not find significant differences in salivary amylase levels between individuals with periodontal diseases and those with healthy periodontium. Furthermore, certain studies highlighted the impact of periodontal treatment on salivary amylase levels, noting significant reductions following scaling and root planing in both gingivitis and periodontitis groups.

Discussion

Salivary amylase has gained attention as a potential biomarker for periodontal diseases due to its multifunctional roles in the oral cavity, including enzymatic activity and modulation of bacterial growth (Baik et al., 2013; Fábíán et al., 2012; Ochiai et al., 2014). The studies reviewed in this manuscript provide valuable insights into the diagnostic potential of salivary amylase and its relationship with periodontal disease severity. Although the majority of studies observed

elevated salivary amylase levels in individuals with gingivitis or periodontitis compared to healthy controls, not all of these findings reached statistical significance. The observed variations in results may be attributed to methodological differences, population heterogeneity, and the complexity of disease progression, which warrant further discussion.

One major cause of discrepancies across studies lies in the methodologies used to assess salivary amylase levels. Techniques such as enzymatic assays, immunoassays, or spectrophotometric methods vary in their sensitivity and specificity (Ohta, Noda, & Sakurada, 2019), potentially leading to inconsistent results. These inconsistencies could also be influenced by saliva collection protocols. Although all included studies collected unstimulated saliva, factors such as timing of collection, diet, physical activity, and pre-analytical handling can also influence salivary amylase levels (Robert-Mercier, Dehoux, Longrois, & Guglielminotti, 2014).

Another critical factor contributing to variability is the heterogeneity of study populations. Differences in demographic characteristics, such as age and sex likely influence salivary amylase expression. The effect of age on salivary amylase

levels remains inconclusive, with some studies reporting no age-related differences (Chauncey, Borkan, Wayler, Feller, & Kapur, 1981; Nassar, Hiraishi, Islam, Otsuki, & Tagami, 2014), while others report higher levels (Wang & Woolfolk, 2009) or lower levels in older individuals (Ben-Aryeh et al., 1986).

Salivary amylase also shows promise as a biomarker for assessing the severity and stage of periodontal disease. Its release is linked to sympathetic nervous system activation, which may be triggered by periodontal inflammation. This activation can lead to increased salivary amylase levels, potentially reflecting a protective response to inflammation escalation (Hashim et al., 2024; Hildebrandt et al., 2020). The correlation between salivary amylase levels and clinical parameters, such as clinical attachment loss and pocket depth, further supports its role in monitoring disease progression (Acquier et al., 2015).

The potential of salivary amylase as a biomarker extends beyond diagnosis to post-treatment monitoring. The reductions in salivary amylase levels following scaling and root planing, suggesting that it could serve as an indicator of treatment efficacy. This reduction may reflect decreased systemic inflammation and improved periodontal health (Mani et al., 2023; Neha et al., 2018). However, further research is needed to validate its reliability across different treatment modalities and populations. In addition, understanding the mechanisms underlying amylase level changes post-treatment could enhance its clinical utility.

Conclusion

Salivary amylase demonstrates potential as a biomarker for periodontal health and post-treatment outcomes, though inconsistencies in findings highlight the need for standardized methodologies.

Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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